

CAN TRANSLATION BE USEFUL IN A SECOND LANGUAGE TEACHING? A PROPOSAL FOR USING TRANSLATION IN BILINGUAL PHYSICAL EDUCATION THROUGH CONTENT AND LANGUAGE INTEGRATED LEARNING

Santiago García-Calvoⁱ

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9627-6022>

University of Castilla-La Mancha,
Spain

Abstract:

This work aims to determine the usefulness of translation in FLT (Foreign Language Teaching), to analyze pros and cons of translation and discussing both postulates. It is tried to argue the integrating of translation as a non-linguistic discipline called BPE (Bilingual Physical Education). Therefore, a brief review of translation along history to this day is made and an integrated proposal in BPE-CLIL (Bilingual Physical Education in Content and Language Integrated Learning) is presented that it is addressed to 6th grade of Primary education. After applying the proposal in the educational context, it is shown that there is compatibility and translation can be used in a meaningful way in foreign language teaching regarding non-linguistic disciplines.

Keywords: translation pros and cons; translation integrated; a proposal in bilingual physical education; content and language integrated learning methodology

1. Introduction

1.1 Conceptual Framework

1.1.1 A foreign language in PE using CLIL

The learning of foreign languages has become one of the most interesting objectives in the European education systems. It has been taken into account the legislative framework. The legislative framework talks about a constructive approach. The Council of Europe (2001) establishes the CEFR (Common European Framework of Reference) and gives some guidelines for translation as a communicative competence. In Spain, the LOMCE 8/2013 (Organic law on education) focuses on the process rather than the outcome and regulates knowledge of a foreign language as an important tool in students' training. In spite of the fact that European guidelines effort to promote

ⁱ Correspondence: email santiago.garcíacalvo@edu.jccm.es

learning linguistic, multilingual training remains one of the pending subjects of the most countries. Villarón (2017) states that for some years in Spain, important efforts have been made in the field of teaching a second language, although, in the light of the data, it does not invite optimism. In this line, Coyle (2011, 2013) points out Spain are becoming one of the most experienced countries in the implementation of language immersion programs. Coyle, Hood and Marsh (2010) create the framework for CLIL, known as 4Cs framework (Content, Cognition, Communication and Culture) and its main characteristic is to integrate language learning and content learning. Attard, Walter, Theodorou and Chrysanthou (2015) consider a fifth C, regarding the incorporation of competences.

PE is found as a feasible subject to be considered as a non-linguistic discipline, and therefore, it is considered as one of the subjects more suitable to teach a second language, thanks to its inherent peculiarities (Baena-Extremera, Granero-Gallegos, Baños and Ortíz-Camacho, 2018; Bothman, 2013; Chiva and Isidori, 2018; Faya-Cerqueiro, 2012; García-Calvo, 2015; García-Calvo, 2018; García-Calvo, Banegas and Salaberri, 2019; García-Calvo and Salaberri, 2018; Zindler, 2013). Faya-Cerqueiro (2012) considers that BPE-CLIL (Bilingual Physical Education in Content and Language Integrated Learning) provides an additional support based on oral, visual and motor skills. García-Calvo and Salaberri (2018) point out that in BPE-CLIL students are more stimulated cognitively working integrally several skills. The efficiency will be reflected if we get a proper threshold of difficulty for the student and ongoing feedback lets us set the level of students. Chiva-Bartoll and Salvador-García (2018:23) writes: *“education is a field in constant change... and Physical Education, as a piece fundamental in the integral development of the students, cannot remain alien to the social context”*. As regards FLT (Spanish) in United Kingdom, Zindler (2013) states the combination L2 (second language) and PE help to develop motivation and improve motor and linguistic skills. As regards FLT (Spanish) in United State, Bothman (2013:8) writes *“incorporating Spanish into a physical education program would help prepare young people for the demands of the future”*. Therefore, it would be necessary to break traditional patterns and perform a dual approach known as CLIL and the dual approach does not mean to consider two different subjects (Marsh, 2000). As regards FLT (English) in Spain, García-Calvo (2015) states that students are more motivated using CLIL methodology in PE. In this line, Baena-Extremera et al. (2018) consider PE can contribute to learn a second language (English) and one important way to check it is based on students' satisfaction. Regarding Physical education, Muñoz, Gómez-Lopez and Granero-Gallegos (2019) analyze the fun and the intention of practice in Physical education. They consider the importance of fun and the teachers's role to stimulate student's creativity. Regarding non-linguistic competence, Chanda (2017) considers translation with a multidisciplinary natura belonged to macrolinguistics. Therefore, a comprehensive translation has to offer works in linguistic and non-linguistic disciplines.

1.2 Translation historical review

To contextualize, it is appropriate to make a brief historical review about the evolution of translation along history. Behind the field of translation lie the names and theories emerging at diverse periods. There are changes taking place in the history of translation; however, such changes differ from one place into another. Soler (2013) considers that the history of translation goes back to the ancient times with the distinction of *“verbum pro verbo”* (literal translation or word-for-word) and *“sensum pro sensu”* (free translation or sense-for-sense). Translation theory is scarce in antiquity, and the theories that emerge at the time are unsystematic remarks, mainly situated in the discipline of rhetoric. In fact, the very pioneers of the field are luminary Roman commentators, such as Cicero or Quintilian, who consider translation as a value for the mature orator. In the first c. B.C., Cicero, referring to Latin versions of speeches by the Greek orators, writes: *“I did not translate as an interpreter, but as an orator...I did not hold it necessary to render word-for-word, but I expressed the general style and the force of language”* (Cicero 46 B.C./1960 CE./Hubbel 1949:364). Another period is brought about by St. Jerome in the fourth century B.C., whose approach to translating the Septuagint into Latin would affect later translations of the Scriptures (Munday, 2001). It negated the word-for-word approach, for by closely following the form of the original, the sense of the original is masked and an absurd translation is created.

Munday (2001:20) states *“in translating from the Greek the syntax contains a mystery-I render not word-for-word but sense-for-sense”*. In the seventeenth century, influential theories emerge; the most obvious is that of John Dryden (1631-1700), whose trichotomy on translation types (meta-phrase, para-phrase and imitation) makes big strides. At the outset of the nineteenth century, the Romanticism discusses the issue of translatability and untranslatability. Munday (2001) considers the translator leaves the writer alone as much as possible and moves the reader towards the writer or he leaves the reader alone as much as possible and moves the writer towards the reader. In the mid-twentieth century, the prevalent concept is translatability. The main issue to be tackled by linguists and literary critics is whether the differences that separate the languages and culture can be brought back to friendship via translation or not. From the 1950s, each decade is by a dominant concept such as translatability, equivalence etc. Before the twentieth century, translation is an element of language learning, the study of the field develops into an academic discipline only in the second half of the twentieth century, when this field achieves a certain institutional authority.

1.3 Translation in current educational approaches

Translation studies is now a field, which brings together approaches from a wide language and cultural studies, and for its own use, modifies them and develops new models to its own requirements. The invention of the Internet and the ICT (Information and communication technologies) allows translators to utilize practical techniques.

The usefulness of translation, in the teaching of foreign language, has long been brought into question. When translation is considered as a didactic tool for language

instruction, the controversy is ensured. The ongoing controversy about translation is analyzed as a tool for language instruction. Some authors agree and others disagree in its application, and therefore, some arguments for both cases are discussed. A proposal in a non-linguistic discipline is presented to integrate translation in BPE-CLIL.

Attard et al. (2015:26) write about students' temporary support "*CLIL learning is a process both knowledge and language building... scaffolding is a modular system of metal tubes... It allows building a lot higher than they could get from the ground*". Teachers should bear in mind some strategies to teach a non-linguistic discipline as BPE-CLIL such as imitation, paraphrase, rephrasing and recasting (inter-lingual and intra-lingual communication). They are quite productive and fruitful with young learners because recasting supports children as they are acquiring English, and rephrasing also supports children (Slattery and Willis, 2001).

2. Discussion

It seems difficult to initiate a discussion regarding the publications on this topic. The publications hardly exist in this specific area. However, a discussion can be approached from a broader sense starting from the translation from a general point of view to arrive at the application in a particular non-linguistic discipline. On the one hand, it reflects the authors who are in favor and on the other hand the opinion of the authors who are against.

Valero Garcés (1996) considers translation as a communicative activity called quintessential. In the same vein, Newmark (1991:20) writes: "*translation from L1 (native language) to L2 (second language) and L2 to L1 is recognized as the most important social skill since it promotes communication and understanding between strangers*". A clarification is important since the issue of gender translation is a difficult question which it arises and sometimes prevents communication. Inclusive or non-inclusive context could be the main question related to translation. Empirical studies have demonstrated that English language has changed along the history. As Duff (1989) states translation happens everywhere, all the time, so it can be possible in the classroom. The advantages of using translation in teaching context are addressed by some authors.

Leonardi (2010) considers that translation, in a global world, plays a very important role in an increasingly globalized world and increasingly multilingual Europe where it is used on a daily basis. Translation includes listening and speaking. It is due to teacher and student's interaction discussing problems related to the translation task. Maybe it is not really an advantage since it is a feature of today's society but Ellis (1984) states that translation can be performed orally and in writing since there is no reason why translation exercises could not be used to introduce or practice structures or lexical items. As regards age and level of learners, Duff (1989:7) writes: "*the use of translation is better for advanced learners and good for beginners in teaching vocabulary*". Translation is natural since it is a natural comparison between the target and native languages of students, thus it fosters decoding of difficult target language structures

and elements. Schöffner (1998) states that the use of translation elicits structures that otherwise would be avoided by the students. In relation to comprehension, translation shows an effective comprehension control. From a Psychological point of view, translation is motivating (Fernandez-Guerra, 2014) and requires the acquisition of organized knowledge. As regards communication, translation is a kind of communicative activity which is practiced within a meaningful context (Duff, 1989). Vermes, (2010) says that translation is not only structure manipulation; it is primarily a form of communication. And as such, it necessarily involves interaction and cooperation between people, which makes it a potentially very useful device in foreign language teaching. In this line, Cook (2010) states that translation is sometimes considered the fifth skill, alongside the four other skills and, therefore, it can be a valuable tool to develop and improve communicative competence. Many authors stress the value of using the native language in second language teaching (Aurbach, 2016; Pae, 2012; Schweers, 1999). The interest in using the native language in the English classroom is caused by the necessity to improve language accuracy and fluency. Therefore, the use of native language and translation can serve as a tool for improving language skills. The use would depend on different factors (level, age, teacher, context, etc.). Finally, it would be important to highlight the result of a survey focused on student's perception of translation. The results consider that translation is one of the preferred language learning tasks (Fernandez-Guerra, 2014).

Summarizing the opinion of the majority of authors who are in favor, translation is can be considered a valid tool for language instruction for the following general reasons: firstly, translation helps students to understand the influence of L1 (mother tongue) on L2 (foreign language) and correct errors of misuse of particular words or structures, allowing them to think comparatively; secondly, it involves contrast; it enables us to explore the potential of both languages (L1 and L2); thirdly, it forces students to think carefully about meaning, not just too mechanically manipulate forms; fourthly, it encourages students to take risks rather than avoid them; fifthly, it develops three qualities, which are essential to language learning: accuracy, clarity and flexibility, training the student to search for the most appropriate words to convey what is meant; sixthly, it invites speculation and discussion; seventhly, it develops student' metalinguistic awareness and finally, translation can develop skills in a natural and logical manner (Harris and Sherwood, 1978).

Translation has long been neglected in L2 classrooms. In this line, it was considered an inadequate reminder of old teaching methodologies, especially those derived from the GTM (Grammar Translation Method), the dominant form of language teaching until the 20th century. The main arguments and assumptions that have been provided against the use of translation as a language teaching aid have been pointed by some authors (Duff, 1989; Sharma, 2006; Vermes, 2010). According to the communicative approaches, the use of L1 was considered as undesirable. Duff (1989:6) writes "*translation is not a communicative act and, thus, has nothing to do in a communicative approach to language teaching*". Sharma (2006) states students have to be accustomed to

learning the FL (Foreign Language) without explanations and translation into L1. A monolingual approach maintains that the foreign language should be the only medium of communication in the classroom. Vermes (2010:84) clearly states “*translation is not the aim of language learning, it is the aim of translator training and both are independent fields of study*”. To sum up, they consider that the students’ native language should not be allowed in a second language classroom. However, even if a student’s native language can be seen as a negative transfer, transfer is an important characteristic of second language acquisition (Odlin, 1997). Both negative and positive transfer between native language and second language are essential to develop the intricate process of a student’s second language. The disadvantages of the use of translation in the teaching context are addressed by different researchers. Viqueira (1992) states that the use of L1 involves the risk of create native language dependence. Duff (1989) considers that translation only involves writing and reading. In relation to negative transfer and interference, translation is a constant source of negative transfer and causes interference of the native language and in the same line, translation inhibits thinking in the foreign language L2. Therefore, translation is only appropriate for training translators (Malmkjaer, 1998).

3. A proposal for using translation in Bilingual Physical Education

The social demand for language learning is a reality worldwide and educators may wonder whether it would be possible to integrate a skill as translation in order to improve communication in BPE-CLIL. The answer does not like easy. On the one hand, it looks like practically unlikely since PE is a practical subject based on movement. On the other hand, CLIL is a flexible approach that allows using translation at specific moments (at the beginning of a didactic unit, at the end, rainy days...).

A proposal for using translation is designed for students of 6th grade of Primary Education. The main consist in integrating translation and several skills. For this purpose, a famous futsal coach was interviewed at School.

3.1 Proposal Arguments

Translation is all around us as an authentic act of communication, so we find it in notices, labels, menus, subtitles, news interviews and many other places. It helps students in lexicon and grammatical problems and can be positive if we use it to get specific aims; it is a useful tool in itself, it will not be the panacea, but it can be an important tool in a globalized world and multilingual society; it is a pedagogic tool in a foreign language and we can integrate translation with other skills; translation activity should serve as a communicative purpose trying to join several skills and it should not be the best or as much hated lately. Advantages should surpass disadvantages. As regards the learning and teaching process in BPE, García-Calvo (2015) states that the teacher must not worry about perfect comprehension since it is not forbidden to speak in the mother tongue since if the students use a hybrid form (at the beginning) it is the

evidence of progress which is a key characteristic of second language learning. The breakdown in communication develops noticing and negotiation of meaning. In BPE are followed three SLA (Second Language Acquisition) conditions: comprehensible input, creating opportunities to negotiate meaning and motivating learners. In BPE-CLIL the students need to practice the four skills (reading, listening, writing and speaking). Notwithstanding, It is not refused the use of translation since it is not counterproductive to the development of the four skills.

3.2 Jesus Velasco´s interview (text of listening material)

Good morning and hello everyone; it is a pleasure for me to introduce Javier Velasco. He is a Futsal Coach. He studied Physical Education and he has got a degree in PE. When he was young, he studied at this School, like his children.

Teacher- How are you?

Coach- Fine, thanks so much

Teacher- Congratulations for your futsal planets award in 2014, 2015, 2016 and 2017 your recent European cup award in April, 2018.

Coach- I am happy for being considered some years the best futsal coach in the world

Teacher- By the way. Do you think that healthy habits prevent diseases?

Coach- I could tell you general recommendations to do sports. You have to take an interest in healthy habits to prevent diseases.

Teacher- What is fair play for you?

Coach- Fair play consists in showing respect for your opponents. You have to win, but respecting opponents and rules.

Teacher- When did you begin to play football?

Coach- When I was younger; I liked to play games at my School´s playground. Then, I was an International Futsal player. For that, I decided to be a Futsal Coach and worked as a Coach.

Teacher- What would you like to do in your free time?

Coach- I would like to relax. Trekking and traveling as a family relax me since I have very little time to enjoy with my children and my wife.

Teacher- What is your records?

Coach- National Championship Winner in Italy (1998-1999, 2001-2002, 2002-2003, 2006-2007, 2007-2008, 2008-2009). National Cup Winner in Italy 2001-2008). National-Super Cup Winner 1998, 2002, 2003, 2007 and 2008. Best Club Coach of the World (2014, 2015, 2016, 2017). Futsal award 2018 (European Champion with Inter Movistar´s team).

Teacher- Congratulations and thanks so much for coming today.

Finally, students have to do two activities, a multiple choice test and translate into L1.

3.3 Multiple choice test (objective test)

You are going to listen to Jesus Velasco´s interview. For 1-6 choose your answer from the list of (a-d) Look at the map and then match the correct answer. The students did pre-listening activities working in class around this topic.

1. *Students play games a. best Club Coach of the World.*
2. *Healthy habits b. in playground.*
3. *Fair play c. prevents diseases.*
4. *Jesus Velasco is the d. consists of respecting for the opponents.*
5. *Teacher is*
6. *Professional players play games*

3.4 The teacher shows the interview on a digital white board. The students have to translate into Spanish (direct translation)

4. Conclusion

This work has been written with the explicit purpose of reflecting about the use of translation in a non-linguistic discipline as PE-in-English. This essay has attempted to show that translation can benefit students by increasing their own learning potential. As a result, the conclusion of this assignment has been organized around these aspects discussed previously.

Conclusions after the study and the practical application of the proposal show that the flexibility of CLIL enable to apply the "sandwich technique", where it is not necessary to teach one hundred percent in L2, as sometimes it is necessary to resort to L1. It relies on: the level of the students, teaching experience and the complexity of the tasks. The contents have to be selected and the syllabus adjusted as much as necessary (following legislative framework). The ongoing feedback and formative assessment have been helpful in this task.

Translation as a tool has been an aid for communication on the following aspects: to explain the meaning of some words or idioms. Some idioms are difficult to explain in English, e.g., "it is raining cats and dogs", "ball is in your court" "cannot judge a book by its cover", "devil's advocate" and "do not put all your eggs in one basket"; students using translation activities have become aware of L1 and L2 patterns and the correspondence between them (6th grade students had an A2 level of CEFRL).

Translation exercise improves communication. As long as translation is adapted to the student (age, interests, level, context...) and integrated with other skills in the classroom. Edge (1986) points out, there is no reason why a translation class should not benefit from a communicative and interactive approach.

The way in which the teacher speaks can create opportunities for learning in an EFL (English Foreign Language) in classroom. Communication is a phenomenon which is central to classroom activities. Interaction is the key and we should use caretaker talk, that is, the language used by teachers when addressing young children. This is characterized by a series of modifications or adaptations to make it easier for the children to understand (pitch, clearer pronunciation, explanations, repetitions, examples, short translations...).

Translation is one of the oldest methods in second language teaching. Translation can be a useful pedagogic device in order to improve communication. Translation can also be integrated with teaching functions in the foreign language. In class, it is advisable to use L1 from time to time to clarify some students' doubts (scaffolding) regarding the topic, context or specific activities. There should be flexibility to use both sources (L1-L2 or L2-L1), especially at beginner level. Activities and tasks are promoting to develop the learning in Physical Education. Contents and communicative aspects are vital. As regard treatment errors, they are a vital part of the learning process. Correction has to be used in a positive way. Nevertheless, it is necessary a golden rule and we must not let students get lazy.

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Conflict of interest

The author does not state conflict of interest.

About the author

Santiago García-Calvo is a permanent civil servant in the Minister of Education, Spain, who has been awarded the first place. He has got TKT-CLIL certificate (Cambridge Assessment English). He holds a degree in English and Physical Education from Castilla-La Mancha and Complutense Universities, MA in TEFL from University of Jaen and PhD candidate. He has published a book regarding bilingual Physical education and some articles in several international ranking journals. His research interest includes content and language integrated learning and didactic of education regarding searching effective methods in teaching and learning processes.

References

- Attard Montalto S., Walter L., Theodorou M. and Chrysanthou, K. (2015). CLIL guide Book. *Lifelong Learning Programme*, 1-51.
- Auerbach, E. R. (2016). Reexamining English only in the ESL classroom. *Tesol Quarterly*, 50, 4 doi. 10.1002/tesq.310

- Baena-Extremera, A., Granero-Gallegos, A., Baños, R. and Ortíz-Camacho, M. (2018). Can Physical Education contribute to learning English? Structural model for self-determination theory. *Sustainability*, 10, 3613. doi: 10.3390/su10103613
- Bothman, M. (2013). *Bilingual Physical Education*. Thesis. Western Oregon University: Oregon.
- Chanda, V. M. (2017). Issues in Translation as a Multidisciplinary Field. *International Journal of Humanities and cultural studies*, 4, 3, 49-61
- Chiva-Bartoll, O. and Salvador-García, C. (2018). Educación Física y pluringüismo: una mirada al futuro inmediato. *International Journal of Sports Humanities*, 1, 23-32.
- Cicero, M. T. (1949). *De inventione, De optimo genere oratum, Topica*. Edited and translated by M. Hubbell. Cambridge (MA): Harvard University Press.
- Cook, G. (2010). *Translation in Language Teaching: An argument for reassessment*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Council of Europe. (2001). *Common European Framework of Reference*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Coyle D. (2011). *Teacher Education and CLIL Methods and Tools*. Seminary in Arisaig, Scotland. Retrieved from <http://www.crem.it/public/documenti/seminar.pdf>
- Coyle, D. (2013). Listening to learners: an investigation into successful learning across CLIL contexts. *International Journal of Bilingual Education and Bilingualism*, 16, 3, 244-266. doi: [10.1080/13670050.2013.777384](https://doi.org/10.1080/13670050.2013.777384)
- Coyle, D., Hood, P., and Marsh, D. (2010). *CLIL. Content and Language Integrated Learning*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Duff, A. (1989). *Translation*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Edge, J. (1986). Acquisition disappears in adultery: interaction in the translation classroom. *ELT Journal*, 40, 121-124.
- Ellis, R. (1984). *Classroom second language development*. Oxford: Pergamon.
- Faya-Cerqueiro, F. (2012). Influencia de una asignatura de inglés para fines específicos en posibles profesores de AICLE. *Congreso Internacional de Propuestas docentes en AICLE*. Pamplona: Servicio de Publicaciones de la Universidad de Navarra.
- Fernández-Guerra, A. (2014). The Usefulness of Translation in Foreign Language Learning: Students. Forum. *International Journal of Translation studies*, 2, 153-170.
- García-Calvo, S. (2015). *CLIL curriculum design in Physical Education: transforming theory into practice*. Thesis. University of Jaen: Jaen. Retrieved from <https://hdl.handle.net/10953.1/2229>
- García-Calvo S. (2018). Didactic Proposal in Bilingual Physical Education on Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL). Team Sports. *European Journal of Physical Education and Sport Science*, 4, 5, doi:10.5281/zenodo.1239870
- García-Calvo, S. Banegas, D.L. and Salaberri, M. S. (2019). Satisfaction's study in Bilingual Physical Education after applying a schedule based on content and language integrated learning. *Sportis, Scientific Technical Journal of School Sports, Physical Education and Psychomotricity*, 5, 2, 305-322

- García-Calvo, S. and Salaberri, M.S. (2018). *Educación Física bilingüe en el siglo XXI. Investigación-acción. Análisis de satisfacción en Educación Física bilingüe y no bilingüe*. Berlin: Editorial Académica Española.
- Harris, B. and Sherwood, B. (1978). Translating as an innate skill. In Gerver, D. and Sinaiko (eds.). *Language, Interpretation and Communication*. New York. Plenum Press, 155-170.
- Leonardi, V. (2010). *The Role of Pedagogical Translation in Second Language Acquisition. From theory to practice*. Bern: Peter Lang.
- LOMCE: "Ley orgánica 8/2013, de 9 de diciembre, de Educación". BOE nº 295 de 10 diciembre 2013, 97858-97921. (National law on education).
- Malmkjær K. (1998). Introduction: Translation and Language Teaching. In K. Malmkjær (ed.), *Translation and Language Teaching: Language Teaching and Translation*, Manchester: St. Jerome Publishing.
- Marsh, D. (2000). *Using languages to learn and learning to use languages*. University of Jyväskylä: Finland.
- Munday, J. (2001). *Introducing Translation Studies: Theories and Applications*. London and New York: Routledge.
- Muñoz González, V., Gómez-López, M. and Granero-Gallegos, A. (2019). Relación entre la satisfacción con las clases de Educación Física, su importancia y utilidad y la intención de práctica del alumnado de Educación Secundaria Obligatoria. *Revista Complutense de Educación*, 30, 2, 149-161.
- Newmark, P. (1991). *About Translation: Multilingual Matters*. Clevedon, Philadelphia: Multilingual Matters Ltd.
- Odlin, T. (1997). *Language Transfer*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Pae, H.K. (2012). Linguistic Relativity Revisited: The Interaction between L1 and L2 in Thinking, Learning, and Production. *Psychology*, 3, 1, 49-56.
- Schäffner, C. (1998). Skopos Theory. In Baker, N. (ed.). (1998). *The Routledge Encyclopaedia of Translation Studies*. London: Routledge.
- Sharma, K. (2006). Mother tongue use in English classroom. *Journal of NELTA*, 11 (1-2), 80-87.
- Slattery, M. and Willis, J. (2001). *English for Primary Teachers*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Soler, B. (2013). Translation Studies: An Introduction to the History and Development of Translation. *LINGUAX*. Alfonso X el Sabio University: Madrid, 1-24.
- Schweers, C. (1999). Using L1 in the L2 Classroom. *English Teaching Forum*, 37, 6-13.
- Valero Garcés, C. (1996). L1 y L2 en el aula de idiomas: la lengua materna como complemento metodológico en la enseñanza de segundas lenguas. *BABEL (AFIAL)*, 3/4/5, 187-197.
- Vermes, A. (2010). Translation in Foreign Language Teaching: A Brief Overview of Pros and Cons. *Eger Journal of English Studies*, 10, 83-93.

- Villarón, M.G. (2017). English in compulsory education. A comparative view of the cases of Spain and the Netherlands. *Revista Española de Educación Comparada*, 30, 61-76, doi: 10.5944/reec.30.2017.18694
- Viqueira, M.^a J. (1992). Revalidación de la traducción como elemento de trabajo en el inglés Científico. En Sandi Michele de Oliveira (ed.). *Actas del II Congreso Luso-espanhol de Línguas Aplicadas ás Ciências*. Universidad de Évora: Évora, 76-78.
- Zindler, K. (2013). *Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) and PE in England. An Exploratory Study*. Thesis. University of Sheffield: Sheffield.

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